

Check Point Harmony Endpoint Protection Evaluation against CIS Controls v8.1 Control 10: Malware Defenses

By: Prima Fariz Ansori, Martin Suhartana

A. Configuration Policy and Agent Check Point Harmony Endpoint Protection

Figure 1 Web and File Protections Policy

Configuration Web and File Protections Policy for all endpoint.

Figure 2 Advanced Options Scan on Web and Files Protection Policy

Configuration Advanced Option Scan for Web and File Protections Policy for all endpoint.

Figure 3 Advanced Options Signatures on Web and Files Protection Policy

Configuration Advance Option Signatures for Web and File Protections Policy for all endpoint.

Figure 4 Behaviour Protection Policy

Configuration Behaviour Protection Policy for all endpoint.

Figure 5 Media Encryption Policy

Configuration Media Encryption Policy for all endpoint.

Figure 6 Configuration Feature Agent Check Point Harmony Endpoint Protection

Configuration Feature Agent for all endpoint.

B. Script Attack

Table I Autorun.inf

```
[autorun]
open=dummy.exe
action=Run dummy file
label=Test USB Autorun
icon=dummy.ico
```

This Script is for testing attack using autorun.inf placed on USB.

Table II Script Edit Registry

```
reg add
HKEY_LOCAL_MACHINE\SOFTWARE\WOW6432Node\CheckPoint\accepted_cn\ /v -
-Fingerprint-- /t REG_SZ /d "MICE KERN JILL RUG USED DEBT LILY ABET TEST
DID FLAK WEAK"
```

This Script for testing attack edit Registry.